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Title: GC Q – Exactive: Evaluation, Calibration and Tune

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Summary

This section describes Tune, Evaluation and Calibration of GC Q - Exactive

- Always make a note about positive or negative calibration of the MS to the Log Book
- If you do any changes in window, click **Apply** or select the Hot link check box to apply all changes in real time
- Always check the parameters the Repeller voltage and Lens voltage (1-3), see typical parameters **Figure 2**

Preparing MS for Tune/Evaluation/Calibration

1. In Thermo Q Exactive GC program choose File > Load Tune File and select a Tune file with given parameters

2. In thermos Q Exactive GC program click the **On** button

- Turn the Filament **On** and wait for a while (let to "burn" for a few minutes to "clean" the filament) and then Turn **Off**
- Turn the calibration gas to **EI** and wait for stabilization. Turn the Filament **On** and wait for signal stabilization. In Instrument Status > TIC Variation should be ~ 2% (maximum 5%)

NOTE: Turn on calibration gas first and then filament. In case the air is blown out instead of calibration gas the air contact with the filament is prevented

NOTE: If the system was in Off mode before, it is necessary to put the instrument into On mode for at least 90 minutes before a mass calibration is performed. The filament and calibration gas do not need to be on during this time

EI/CI source		actual
MS transfer line temp. (°C)	250	250
Ion source temp. (°C)	200	200
Filament	On	
Calibration gas	EI	
Ionization mode	EI	
CI gas flow (mL/min)	0.00	0.00
CI gas port	None	
CI gas type	None	

Apply Help Hot link

- Injection time (**IT**) in *ms* is typically less than **5 ms** and height of the largest peak (**NL**) is typically greater than **1 E8** see **Figure. 1**.
- Check that all calibration masses are visible: **68.995; 99.993; 130.991; 196.983; 218.985; 263.986; 413.977; 501.970** see **Figure 1**.

Figure 1. Spectrum of calibration masses

To Tune GC Q - Exactive

- 1) In Thermo Q Exactive GC program click **On** button to turn mass spectrometer On mode
- 2) Turn **On** calibration gas and filament as described before (in section Preparing MS for Tune/Evaluatio/Calibration)
- 3) Click the title bar of the Tune window to display it
- 4) Choose **TIC**
- 5) In the tune window click the **Tune** to start automatic tune procedure
- 6) After tune save the current Tune report (File > Save Tune File as EI_20201102_KC-IT50_250_280.mstune to C:\Xcalibur\methods)

Figure 2 Typical values of the source parameters

NOTE: Perform Tune before measurement of each batch/every day of measurement. Tune optimize parameters to obtain the best signal intensity.

NOTE: Before each Evaluation/Calibration or after each maintenance perform Tune (check the parameters if it is similar to the previous Tune (Repeller voltage, Lens voltage 2, Lens voltage 1, Lens voltage 3) see Figure 2. A significant change in parameters means, for example, contamination of the source (see SOP_GC_Q_Exactive_ion Source Maintenance)

To Evaluate mass calibration

The evaluation should be performed after each maintenance, switching off mass spectrometer and before each batch/every day of measurement. Evaluation is used to check all parameters on mass spectrometer

- 1) In Thermo Q Exactive GC program click **On** button to turn mass spectrometer On mode
- 2) Turn on the calibration gas and filament as described before (in section Preparing MS for Tune/Evaluation/Calibration)
- 3) Click the title bar of the Evaluate window to display it
- 4) Positive Ion Evaluation/Negative Ion and Extra Evaluation (if you plan to measure in one ionization mode, typically select this type of ionization for evaluation).

NOTE: Evaluation can be performed either all at once step or step by step (recommended)

> Base Evaluation > Isolation Evaluation > Mass Check > Leak Check > Electronic > EI/CI Ion

Source Evaluation

Example of positive Evaluation mode:

Pos Ion Evaluation

> Base Evaluation ✓

> Isolation Evaluation ✓

> Iso Mass/Res. Eval. ✓

> Quadrupole isolation shape check ✓

> Q Transmission Evaluation ✓

> Mass Check ✓

> Leak Check ✓

> Create EI Tune Report ✓

> Evacuate Vacuum Inlet ✓

Extra Evaluation

> Electronic ✓

> Quadrupole RF Frequency ✓

> Inject Flatapole RF ✓

> Bent Flatapole RF ✓

> HCD RF ✓

> Long-term Mass Accuracy Test ✗

> Isolation Transmission Endurance test ✓

> EI/CI Ion Source Evaluations ✓

> Evacuate Vacuum Inlet ✓

> Leak Check ✓

> Create EI Tune Report ✓

NOTE: Long-term Mass Accuracy Test takes too long and it is not necessary to perform it at each evaluation

5) Click **Evaluate** to start the automatic evaluation procedure

6) After evaluation click **OK** to close message box

NOTE: If evaluation fails, please perform calibration (only for fault parameter)

To calibrate GC Q - Exactive

Perform calibration after fault evaluation or after the specified time has elapsed. Calibration is used to calibrate mass spectrometers parameters and mass calibration

- 1) In Thermo Q Exactive GC program click **On** button to turn mass spectrometer On mode
- 2) Turn on the calibration gas and filament as described before (in section Preparing MS for Tune/Evaluation/Calibration)
- 3) Click the title bar of the Calibrate window to display it

- 4) Choose parameter that needs to be calibrated: Base Calibration, Electronic, Basics – Positive Ion, Isolation mass and Res. (pos)/(neg), Mass Calibration (pos)/(neg)
- 5) In the Calibrate window, click the **Calibrate** to start the automatic calibration procedure
- 6) After calibration click **OK** to close message box (In case of incorrect calibration, repeat the calibration of the given parameter)
- 7) After calibration put the mass spectrometer to Standby mode

NOTE: Any time the system is placed in standby of off, the calibration gas and filament are turned off.

Troubleshooting

1. Problem with quadrupole calibration

Figure 3. Problem with quadrupole calibration (Quad iso Mass/Res. (narrow))

1. Recalibrate according Q-Exactive recommendations (see Figure 3). Switch to Advanced User Role and calibrate in this order:
 - a. Quadrupole RF Frequency
 - b. Quad RF freq. fine adjustment
 - c. Quad Iso Mass/Res Cal (rough)
 - d. Iso Mass/Res. Cal (wide iso)
 - e. Iso Mass/res. Cal (narrow)